

Pest management practices used by farmers in some parts of Owerri North L.G.A Imo State

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ABSTRACT:

Pest management is one of the major problems faced in Nigeria. This study was done to assess pest management practices in Owerri North L.G.A, Imo State. A structured questionnaire was developed focusing on the pest and disease the individuals were facing in the study area and their method of management. Two hundred questionnaires were randomly distributed to the individual in the study area. The result revealed the good awareness of pest management with 165(92.69%) respondents. The household pests list in the questionnaire were identified between (94.94%)-(100%) of the respondents. Result revealed that more than a half of the respondents had a food crop farm with 93.26%. The study revealed that all the respondents had encountered household pests, however, mosquito 178 (100%) being the most acknowledge. Ninety for point Ninety four percent of the respondents acknowledged that their crop are affected by pest. The result showed that more than 50(50%) of the pest are seen during the rainy season with a frequency of 101 (56.74%). The result on the different control measures practiced by the respondents revealed that, traditional method had the highest frequency of 166 (93.26%) among other methods. However, 51.69% considered their effectiveness of the control method moderate. The Result on the impact of pesticides showed that 93 (52.25%) and 96 (53.93) acknowledged that the use of pesticides in the area affects both soil and human. It was observed that most of the problem of pest management in the area of study can be solved by creating schools or awareness in the communities so that farmers will be educated on the types of pest and how to remedy their attacks on crops and livestock.

Keywords: *Pest management practices, farmers, pest, pesticides*

INTRODUCTION:

Scientific percentage of people in developing countries engage themselves in agriculture, but the yields of their products are low due to pest and disease that plague their crops, (Adejuni, 2005). The agricultural sector is the means of livelihood of most of the rural population and the key to food security and poverty reduction. The sector comprises six sub sectors namely, food crops, industrial crops, horticulture, livestock, fisheries and forestry. The horticulture subsector has grown in the last decade to become a major foreign exchange earner, employer and contributor to food security in the country.

Shortly after World War II, when synthetic insecticides become widely available, entomologist in California developed the concept of "supervised pest control management, Smith (2004). Around the same time, insect control was supervised by qualified entomologists and insecticides application were based on conclusions reached from periodic monitoring of pest and natural

Alternative to calendar based programmes. Supervised control was based on knowledge of ecology and analysis of projected trends in pest and natural enemy population. Pests damage crops at different stages of growth on the field, at harvest during transportation and in storage. This leads to 5 -40% crop loss yearly and has a serious effect on the food security for the ever-increasing population of the country. The management of pests in crops to obtain better yield is paramount for food security. The resource-poor farmers who produce a large percentage of the crop for consumption cannot afford expensive management of pests in order to meet the yearly target consumption level for the country. There are several documented evidence on pest and its management practices in Nigerian and sparsely in Imo State. A detailed understanding of the health management practices is invaluable in accessing the cause or pest burden and in development of community based pest control programmes in the country. Holistic profiling of the pest and management practices in

all the communities of Imo State is invaluable, since pest does not observe boundary. Hence a mismanagement of pest poses a problem in an area leading to the production of poor yields as well as causing disease in human and livestock.

The practice of pest management in Owerri North L.G.A of Imo State not been documented to the best of my knowledge. Therefore filling the gap is the aim of this project, this will be invaluable in mounting the pest program and educating the communities on the sound management practices of pest.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Area description:

This study was carried out in Owerri North L.G.A which is one of the Local Government Areas of Imo State, Nigeria. Its headquarters is in the town of Uratta. It has an area of 198 square km and a population of 175,395 at the 2006 census. The postal code of the area is 460. Owerri North is semi-urban government area. It encircles Owerri Municipal like a peninsular. Six major roads that lead out of the municipal cuts across Owerri North Communities. In the North, Orlu road leads to Amakaohia and Akwakuma communities. In the East, Okigwe road leads to Orji Community. In the West, MCC road off Wetheral to Obibi Uratta and Ihitaoha communities. In the South, Mbaise road leads to Egbu and Emekuku communities, while Aba road leads to Nazi, Agbala and Ulakwo communities. It has a Latitude of 5.4567° or $5^{\circ}27'24.3''$ north and Longitude of 7.1027° or $7^{\circ}6'9.8''$ east with the elevation 115 metres (377 feet) with farmers dominating the area. Owerri North has seven district; Egbu, Emelsuku, Emii, Ihite/ogala/Oha, Naze, Obibi-Uratta and Orji with Projection of 167.3 km Area and $1,451/km^2$ Population Density (2016).

Study Population:

This study population consist of residents of the selected five villages in Owerri North Local Government Area, who have farm lands where they cultivate crops, rear livestock. They includes Egbu, Emi and Emekuku.

Sampling Techniques:

A multi-staged sampling procedure was employed to select respondents for the study. In the first stage, five out of the villages in the Owerri North L.G.A were selected based on convenience. The chosen communities were; Egbu, Emekuku and Emii. The Second step was to identify some representatives of the Ministry of agriculture and rural development so as to know the farmers involved in the agriculture, while the third stage was to carry out the research Study Sample and Sample Intensity A total of 200 respondents from the various communities were selected for the study. This was done through simple random selection. The distribution of

questionnaire was not equal in each settlement because the number of farmers available for the study was not equivalent.

Data Collection:

The questionnaire was divided into two sections. Section A, solicitate for information on demographical characteristics of the respondents. Primary data was obtained from a structured questionnaire containing close-ended questions on the respondent's socio-demographic characteristics which includes: sex, age, occupation and Education etc. Section B, contain open and closed-ended questions which were made to answer the research questions, which includes; the type of pests and disease encountered by respondents in their various homes and farm lands, the knowledge about pest, the types of pest seen in their locality, the various control methods employed by the respondents, the extents to which the pest cause damages. How often are pest controlled? How effective are control methods? How would you rank access with the use of pesticides? Does use of pesticides affects soil fertility Other information obtained from-the respondents, are the extent to which the practice are documented. A total of 200 questionnaires were administered. Further, a key informant interview using an interview guide was conducted.

Finally, observations and field visits were made by the researcher "to collect relatively objective information on the state of pest infestation on agricultural production. Secondary data was collected from journals articles, desktop surveys, magazine articles, websites publications and published thesis.

Data Analytical:

The qualitative data obtained from the questionnaire survey was analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency, percentages, and tables)

RESULTS:

The demographic characteristic (table 1) shows that there were 119(66.85%) male respondent while 59(33.15%) were females. More than half of the respondents fall within the age range of 30-39 years 66 (37.08%). The age group 20-29 years accounted for 23(12.92%), 41 (23.03%) were within 40-49 while 48(26.97%) were with 50years and above. The occupational profile of the respondents showed that 28(15.73%) were traders and farmers were 68(38.20%), while 18(10.11%) and 30(16.85%) were students and civil servants respectively, while others such as businessmen etc accounted for 34 (19.10%). Marital status showed that 52(29.21%) were single, 84(47.19%) were married, 30(16.85%) divorced, while 12(6.74%) were widowed. The educational level of respondents showed that secondary education has 84(47.19%) which accounted highest level of education

while primary has 34(19.10%), informal education accounts for 54 (24.72%) and 16(8.99%)revealed no formal education. Table 2 revealed that the respondents knowledge of pest. The result showed that 165 respondents had knowledge of pest reflecting a prevalence of 92.69%. The house pest listed in the questionnaires were identified between 94.94% -100% of the respondents. Likewise, the crop pests listed were identified or knowledge 88.76%-99.44% of the respondents. The result in table 3 revealed significant variation on the type of farm owed. The most acknowledged type of farm owed was food crops 93,82%, followed by livestock 89.33%, fishery 56.74%, horticulture 49.34%, forestry 40.54% and industrial crops 38.76%.The result showed that all the respondents assessed had encountered mosquito pest 100%,helminthes revealed 66.85%, tse-tse flies 9.10%, ticks 96.63%, while 98.88% for rodent. Table 4 revealed respondents whose crops were affected by pests in their land. This indicated that out of 178 respondents, 169(94.94%) represent respondent whose crops are affected by pest while 9(5.06%) represent respondent who crops are not affected by pest. result on the distribution of respondents based on the rank or extent of pest problem on their farmland showed that 55.05% ranked the problem of pest on their farm moderate, followed by 25.28% light, 11.79% serious and 7.87% not a problem. Result showed that occurrence of pest is usually high during the rainy season 101(56.74) and 77 (43.26%) during the dry season. The result in table 5 reveals the

response on the use of pesticides and how often the respondents control pest. The result showed that 92.13% of the individuals applied the use of pesticides in their farms while 7.87% do not make use of pesticides. 74.16% acknowledge the application of pest twice in a year, 25.84% four time a year. The result in table 6 revealed several means of controlling pest.93.26% respondents rightly identified the use of traditional control method as a means of controlling pest. Other means of controlling pest mentioned include, cultural method. 85.96%, biological method 49.44%, chemical method 40.45% and integrated pest management 23.03% as means of controlling pest. Result showed on the effectiveness of the control method indicated that 51.69% of respondents acknowledged the effectiveness as moderate, 45.51% serious while 2.80% light. Distribution on the treatment of seeds before planting, revealed that 63.48% of respondent acknowledged the treatment of seeds before sowing while 36.52% do not treat seeds before sowing. Table 7 result on the effects of pesticides showed that 93(52.25%) and 96(53.93%) acknowledged that the use of pesticides in the area affects both soil and human, while 85(47.75%). and 82(46.07%) do not affect the soil, human and its environment. Table 8 result revealed that 61.24% of the respondents did not undergo pest control training while 38.76% participated in pest control training. 50% of respondents never consulted an expert while 44(24.72%) consulted an expert before cultivation and 45(25.28%) during cultivation.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of the respondents.

Variables	Frequency	%
Gender		
Male	119	66.85
Female;	59	33.15
Age Group		
20-29	23	12.92
30-39	66	37.08
40-49	41	23.03
50 above	48	26.97
Occupation		
Student	18	10.11
Trader	28	15.73
Civil Servant	30	16.85
Farmer	68	38.20
Businessmen etc	34	19.10
Marital Status		
Single	52	29.21
Married	84	47.19
Divorced	30	16.85
Widowed	12	6.74
Education		
Primary	34	19.10
Secondary	84	47.19
Informal Education	45	24.72
No Formal Education	16	8.99
Total	178	100

Table 2: Knowledge of pest

Variables	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Do you know what Pest is		
Yes	165	92.70
No	13	7.30
Household Pest		
Ant	10	5.61
Dust mite	11	6.18
Mice	17	9.55
Mosquito	14	7.87
Bed Bug	15	8.42
Flea	18	10.11
Fruit fly	21	11.79
Termite	13	7.30
Cockroach	5	2.81
Fly	10	5.61
Spider	23	5.6
Stink	21	12.92
Crop Pest		
Aphid	10	5.58
Cabbage worm	18	10.11
Blister beetle	17	9.55
Tomato	15	8.42
Horney worm	11	6.18
Leaf hopper	15	8.42
Potato beetle	18	10.11
Wire worm	17	9.55
Cucumber beetle	10	5.58
Root maggot	15	8.42
Grasshopper	32	17.98

Table 3: Type of farm practiced

Variables	Frequency (178)	%
What type of farm do you have?		
Fishery	101	56.74
Livestock	159	89.33
Forestry	72	40.45
Food crops	169	93.82
Industrial crops	69	38.76
Horticulture	88	49.34
What are type of pest and disease encountered in your homes and farmlands		
Mosquito	178	100
Helminthes	119	66.85
Tse-tse flies	123	69.10
Ticks	172	96.63
Rodent	176	98.88

Table 4: Rating and ranking of pest problems

Variables	Frequency (178)	%
Is your crop affected by pests?		
Yes	169	94.94
No	9	5.06
How would you rank problem of pest on your farm		
Serious	21	11.79
Moderate	98	55.06
Light	45	25.28
Not a problem	14	7.87
During which season is pest problem most virulent?		
Rainy season	101	56.72
Dry season	77	43.26
Total	178	100

Table 5: Use of pesticides

Variables	Frequency (178)	%
Do you use pesticides in your farm?		
Yes	164	92.13
No	14	7.87
Total	178	100
How often do you control pest		
Twice in a year	132	74.16
Four time a year	46	25.84
More than four times in a year	0	0.00
Total	178	100

Table 6: Types of pest control method

Variables	Frequency (178)	%
What alternative methods do you use to control pest?		
Chemical method	72	40.45
Traditional method	166	93.26
Biological method	88	49.44
Cultural methods	153	85.96
Integrated pest management	41	23.03
How effective are your control methods?		
Serious	81	45.51
Moderate	92	51.69
Light	5	2.80
Do you treat the seed before Sowing		
Yes	113	63.48
No	65	36.52
Total	178	100

Table 7: Effect of pesticides

Variables	Frequency (178)	%
Does use of pesticides affect soil fertility		
Yes	93	52.25
No	85	47.75
Does use of pesticides affect		
Yes	96	59.93
No	82	46.07
Total	178	100

Table 8: Training and consultation of experts

Variables	Frequency (178)	%
Have you undergone any training on pest control?		
Yes	69	38.76
No	109	61.24
How often do you meet experts for consultation to control pests?		
Before cultivation	44	24.72
During cultivation	45	25.28
Never	89	50.00
Total	178	100

DISCUSSION:

The findings in this study reviewed that some respondents were part-time Farmers who were mostly traders and civil servants. This development agrees with the findings of Iwunze and Amaechi, 2019; Emaikwu et al; 2011, in Imo and Kadunna Respectively. This observation could probably be due to the fact that traders and civil servants who are in poultry farming do so to supplement their

sources of income. Results obtained from the knowledge of pest revealed that 165 respondents had knowledge of pest reflecting a prevalence of (93%). The household pests listed in the questionnaires were identified between (95%-100%) of the respondents. Likewise, the crop pest listed were identified by (89%-99%) of the respondents. Most of the farmers showed a degree of awareness about the insect pests that are attacking their planted crops.

However in most cases they come across the common insect pest like grasshoppers, termites, blister beetle, armyworm, tomato hornworm, ant, cockroaches, spider, fly, mice and aphids etc. The extent of damage caused by the insect pest was quite varied according to the opinions of the farmers. Some of them claimed that the pests causes only minor damages to their crops, simply because of the types of control measures they applied or adopted. (93.82%) of respondents cultivate food crops and 89.33% possessed a livestock farm. This is because food crops are mainly for human consumption, people in the area cultivate crops like, cassava, vegetables and fruits etc which they feed on and sometimes are being sold in the market areas to generate income.

The result also showed that all the respondents assessed had encountered mosquito pest 100%, helminthes revealed 66.85% tse-tse flies 69.10%, Ticks 96.63%, while 98.88% for rodent. Prevalence of mosquito is found to be high because it is an endemic area and that abiotic factors of temperature relative humidity altitude and rainfall play a vital role in mosquito development which in turn influences their population density, (Okogun et al., 2005). Environmental changes due to human activities greatly influence the distribution and survival of many mosquito species (Dossou-Yovo et al., 1995; Adeleke et al, 2008). Amusan et al., 2005) opined that the recent increase in agricultural activities and urbanization contributed to the breeding of different mosquito species in southwestern Nigeria. From the data gathered about the knowledge of the respondents on rating and ranking of pest problems, it is seen that 94.94% crops are affected by pest which were ranked and considered moderate and more virulent during the' rainy season. This is because, food crops are mostly planted or cultivated during the rainy season, however some pest are seen to occur during the rainy or wet season due to dirty and slumpy areas that attracts different pest. From this study it is seen that 93.26% respondents rightly identified the use of traditional control method as a means of controlling pest. Other /means of controlling pest mentioned include, cultural method 85.96%, biological method 49.44%, chemical method 40.45% and integrated pest management 23.03%o as means of controlling pest. Result showed on the effectiveness of the control method indicated that 51.69% of respondents, acknowledged the effectiveness as moderate. A diverse number of traditional methods were used by the farmers/to control pests including the use of wood ashes sprinkled around the base of cocoa and kola tree as well as the vegetables which is seen to be effective, and less expensive. Wood ash was also sprinkled on vegetables to keep away caterpillars. The pest of *Corchorus olitorius* (Ewedu) were controlled by sparing a combination of detergent and kerosene mixed with water. Water extracts of the seeds and the leaves of neem tree were used as pest control by

the farmers, as have been previously reported by Schmulterer et al. (1984). Early harvesting of crops is also a traditional method of pest control. Crops like tomato were harvested while they were still green to minimize the effects of rot and fruit cracking. This method also preserved damage by mite worms which attack tomatoes when they begin to ripe. Some individuals claimed that goat and cow dung has proved useful in plant protection, when sprayed on all green plants of vegetable and fruits. Even in the coconut nursery where termites (*Macrotermes bellicosus*) are major pests, goats and cow dung proved effective as pest control. In this study result showed that 92.13%o of the individuals applied the use of pesticides in their farms According to US Environmental (2007) Pesticides are substances that are meant to control pests or weeds. The term pesticide includes all of the following: herbicide, insecticide, insect growth regulator, nematicide, termiticide, molluscicide, pesticide, avicide, rodenticide, predacide, bactericide, insect repellent, animal repellent, antimicrobial, fungicide, disinfectant (antimicrobial), and sanitizer Carolyn Randall (2013). The most common of these are herbicides which account for approximately 80% of all pesticide use. Most pesticides are intended to serve as plant protection products (also Known as crop protection products), which in general, protect plants from weeds, fungi, or insects. In general, a pesticide is a chemical or biological agent (such as a virus, bacterium antimicrobial, or disinfectant) that deters incapacitates, kills, or otherwise discourages pests. Target pests can include insects, plant pathogens, weeds, molluscs, Birds, mammals, fish, nematodes (roundworms), and microbes that destroy property, cause nuisance, or spread disease, or are disease vectors. Although pesticides have benefits, some also have drawbacks, such as potential toxicity to humans and other species. More than half of the respondents acknowledged that the use of pesticides in the area affects both soil and human. If the credits of pesticides Include enhanced economic potential in terms of increased production of food and fibre and amelioration of vector-borne diseases, then their debits have resulted in serious health implications to man and his environment. There is now overwhelming evidence that some of these chemicals do pose a potential risk to humans and other life forms and unwanted side effects to the environment (Forget, 1993; Igbedioh,1991). It was observed that most of the respondents did not undergo pest control training and they never consulted expert to pest control. This could be as a result of lack of training schools or awareness campaign in community that with educate them on different types of pest and more effective way of controlling them.

CONCLUSION:

The findings from the survey have revealed that most of the respondents have the knowledge of pest. Majority of

the respondents in the study area cultivate food crops like cassava, maize, melon, vegetables etc. These crops are grown in a mixed cropping system, whereas aphid, cabbage worm, tomato hornworm, grasshopper, army worm, cockroaches, ant, termite, spider, fly, mosquito, bed bug etc are the major field pest in the area. It is seen in the study area that majority of the respondents' crop is being affected by pest which was ranked moderate and it is more virulent during the rainy season due to the humid and cool temperature. The method of pest control management practiced by the people of Owerri North on livestock, human and crops are traditional method, cultural method, biological method and chemical method. But traditional method to be more effective and practiced the area. Based on finding in the study area, the use of pesticides not only has an effect on the soil fertility but also it affects them and their environment. Individuals residing in this area of study do not undergo training on pest control and they do not consult expert to control pest.

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